

Deep subsurface sulfate reduction and methanogenesis in the Iberian Pyrite Belt revealed through geochemistry and molecular biomarkers

F. Puente-Sánchez¹, M. Moreno-Paz¹, L. A. Rivas¹, P. Cruz-Gil¹, M. García-Villadangos¹, M. J. Gómez¹, M. Postigo¹, P. Garrido¹, E. González-Toril¹, C. Briones¹, D. Fernández-Remolar², C. Stoker³, R. Amils^{2,4}, and V. PARRO¹.

¹ Departments of Molecular Evolution, Centro de Astrobiología (INTA-CSIC), Madrid, Spain

² Planetology and Habitability, Centro de Astrobiología (INTA-CSIC), Madrid, Spain

³ NASA Ames Research Center, Moffett Field, CA, USA

⁴ Centro de Biología Molecular “Severo Ochoa” (UAM-CSIC), Cantoblanco, Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

The Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB, southwest of Spain), the largest known massive sulfide deposit, fuels a rich chemolithotrophic microbial community in the Río Tinto area. However, the geomicrobiology of its deep subsurface is still unexplored. Herein, we report on the geochemistry and prokaryotic diversity in the subsurface (down to a depth of 166 m) of the Iberian Pyritic belt using an array of geochemical and complementary molecular ecology techniques. Using an antibody microarray, we detected polymeric biomarkers (lipoteichoic acids and peptidoglycan) from Gram-positive bacteria throughout the borehole. DNA microarray hybridization confirmed the presence of members of methane oxidizers, sulfatereducers, metal and sulfur oxidizers, and methanogenic Euryarchaeota. DNA sequences from denitrifying and hydrogenotrophic bacteria were also identified. FISH hybridization revealed live bacterial clusters associated with microniches on mineral surfaces. These results, together with measures of the geochemical parameters in the borehole, allowed us to create a preliminary scheme of the biogeochemical processes that could be operating in the deep subsurface of the Iberian Pyrite Belt, including microbial metabolisms such as sulfate reduction, methanogenesis and anaerobic methane oxidation.

INTRODUCTION

The geomicrobiology of subsurface environments is a matter of growing interest not only for the understanding of life in the absence of light and its role in biogeochemical cycles, but also as a model for searching for life in other planetary bodies where the surface conditions preclude any form of life. The Río Tinto fluvial basin (southwestern Spain) is an acidic system in continuous geological evolution dating back from more than 2 million years (Fernández-

Remolar et al., 2005; Fernández-Remolar & Knoll, 2008). It emerges in the Rio Tinto Anticline region, which is a complex geological structure that is part of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) (Leistel et al., 1997). Its formation is associated with the building up of a Carboniferous volcano-sedimentary complex exposed to a late intensive event of hydrothermal activity that mineralized the volcanic systems. Superficial and subsurface microbial communities sustained on sulfur and iron chemolithotrophy (Amils et al., 2007) have been using the ancient hydrothermal materials as energy sources for millions of years. The microbial activity accelerates the oxidation of the pyrite ore body with the subsequent release of protons, which account for the extreme acidic conditions (pH could be a consequence of microbial activity (Fernández-Remolar et al., 2012).

During the Mars Astrobiology Research and Technology Experiment (MARTE) project (Stoker et al., 2008), four boreholes (BH) in the iron-sulfide deposits at Pena de Hierro, an abandoned mine site located in the catchment area of the Río Tinto, were performed: BH1, BH4, BH8, and BH7 with depths of 59, 166.35, 166, and 5 m, respectively. The objectives were the development of technology for in situ drilling and life detection in planetary exploration, as well as a preliminary geochemical and geomicrobiological characterization of the subsurface. It was a project of marked astrobiological character with a strong technological component, with drilling, aseptic sampling, and searching for microbial activities in a sulfide deposit as the main challenges. Previous published studies from MARTE were focused on the drilling, life detection technology development (Stoker et al., 2008; Parro et al., 2008), and geochemical and mineralogical analyses (Fernández-Remolar et al., 2008a, b). In Parro et al. (2008), we reported the results of a field testing of the SOLID2 instrument for the analysis of BH7 (shallow drill up to 5 m). The objective was instrument validation, and very limited biological information was presented.

In the present work, we focus on the anaerobic part of the BH8 (below ca. 90 m below the surface of the IPB) and present novel and substantial information about: (i) the geochemistry, particularly the determination of organic acids (acetate, formate, oxalate) and nitrate, nitrite, and sulfate anions; (ii) the detection of complex organic matter and microbial biopolymers; and (iii) the microbial community.

The application of molecular ecology techniques is critical to elucidate the geomicrobiology of deep subsurface environments. The heterogeneity (Haldeman et al., 1993) of mineral subsurface samples and the inherent bias of each technique make the combination of several complementary or even redundant approaches especially useful for this purpose. In a previous work (Rivas et al., 2008), we described an antibody microarray-based biosensor containing more than 200 antibodies against bacterial and archaeal strains, crude natural

extracts, cellular proteins and polysaccharides, and other biomolecules. We reported the usefulness of the EMCHIP200 (for Environmental Monitoring CHIP) for immunoprofiling of environmental samples. Additionally, we tested an updated version of the chip (LDChip300, for Life Detector Chip with 300 antibodies) for subsurface life exploration during different drilling campaigns (Parro et al., 2011; Blanco et al., 2012). On the other hand, we demonstrated the usefulness of a small oligonucleotide microarray (the PAM microarray) to explore the prokaryotic diversity at various challenging environments (Garrido et al., 2008; Parro et al., 2011; Blanco et al., 2012). In the present work, the complementary analysis of core samples with multiple molecular ecological tools, such as antibody microarrays (e. g. LDChip), oligonucleotide arrays (PAM microarray), and sequencing, allowed us to infer the relationship between the geochemistry, the prokaryotic diversity, and the potential metabolisms in this deep subsurface environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drilling and sampling

During the 2004 field campaign of the MARTE project, a joint project between NASA Ames Research Center (funded by NASA's ASTEP program) and the Centro de Astrobiología (INTA-CSIC), a 164-m-depth borehole was created using a wireline drilling system (Fernández-Remolar et al., 2008b). Coring was performed with a Boart-Longyear (Salt Lake City, UT, USA) HQ wireline system that produced 60-mm-diameter cores within a plastic liner. A chemical tracer (NaBr) was incorporated into the drilling fluid to identify possible sample contamination produced during drilling by using ion chromatographic analysis of aliquots of the samples analyzed for biology. Cores were retrieved in 1-m sections, encased in plastic liners, placed in sleeves filled with N₂ gas at the drilling site, sealed, and transported to a field laboratory located at the Museo Geominero in the Río Tinto village. In the laboratory, cores were placed and sampled inside a N₂-filled anaerobic chamber as described by Fernández-Remolar et al. (2008b). Briefly, powder samples were extracted from the center of core pieces that were broken open using a core cutter. Samples of rock cuttings were acquired in each 1-m section using a hand-drill and a sterilized bit. Sampling locations were chosen with preference for any parts of the cores that showed evidence of alteration (e.g. oxidation). All elements in contact with rock cores were cleaned and sterilized prior to use on every new sample. Thus obtained, powdered sample was distributed in different sets of tubes as a function of the analysis to be performed, and, once out of the anaerobic chamber, the samples for microbiological and molecular studies were stored frozen (-20°C) or immediately processed. To minimize the

effects of contamination by the drilling fluid, samples in which bromide was detected by ion chromatography were excluded from further analysis.

The aim of this work was the geomicrobiological study of the anaerobic subsurface (below ca. 90 m) of the IPB. Thus, we focused this work on the study of the geomicrobiology associated with the microaerobic and the anaerobic zones of BH8, below the water table, which in BH8 occurred at 90 m depth (Fig. 1; for a geological map of the area, see Fernández-Remolar et al., 2008b; Fig. 1).

Ion chromatography analysis

Core samples were analyzed for the concentrations of inorganic anions such as nitrite, nitrate, and sulfate, and small-molecular-weight organic acids such as acetate, formate, and oxalate using ion chromatography as described (Parro et al., 2011). Briefly, 10 g of sample were sonicated (3 9 1 min cycles) in 20 mL of water, and the mineral particles were removed by centrifugation. Supernatants were collected and loaded into a Metrohm 861 Advanced Compact Ion Chromatographer (Metrohm AG, Herisau, Switzerland) undiluted, or at dilutions values of either 50% or 20%, using a Metrosep A supp 7-250 column, with 3.6 mM sodium carbonate (NaCO₃) as eluent.

Each sample was measured at three different dilutions to ensure that concentration ranges were within the calibration curve for each anion (see below). The measurement error of the equipment for replicate samples was <1%. The concentration ranges for each calibration curve were the following: fluoride, bromide, propionate, formate, phosphate, tartrate, and oxalate from 0.08 (lower limit) to 2 ppm (higher limit); acetate, from 0.2 to 5 ppm; chloride, from 0.4 to 10 ppm; nitrite, from 0.2 to 5 ppm; nitrate from 0.2 to 10 ppm; and sulfate, from 8 to 200 ppm.

Whole crude extract from cores and chemical analysis

Extracts were prepared from 40 g of a sample obtained at 139.38 m depth with GuHCl buffer (4 M guanidine hydrochloride, 0.5 M EDTA, 0.5 M Tris, pH 7.4) following the procedure described by Tuross & Stathoplos (1993). The final extracts were resuspended in sterile distilled water, dialyzed (>1200 Da cutoff) against water, and finally lyophilized. These extracts were used for thin layer chromatography (TLC) fractionation to separate peptidoglycan fragments and lipopolysaccharides (LPS) containing compounds. TLC was run on silica-gel 60 F254 TLC plates (Merck) using isobutyric acid: 1N ammonium hydroxide: water (5:3:2 v/v/v) as solvent, and the detection was performed by short-wave UV fluorescence and by vanillin

staining (Rivas et al., 2008). The spots stained with vanillin were scrapped from the plate, eluted in distilled water, and analyzed by mass spectrometry using electrospray ionization-tandem mass spectrometry (ESI-MS/MS) in the Laboratorio de Espectrometría de Masas (SIDI, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain). Two mass spectrometers were used: an ion trap LCQ Deca XP plus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and a hybrid analyzer, quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) model QSTAR pulsar I (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). The molecular composition was obtained using Elemental composition calculator (Wsearch software, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia) and freely available public software (e.g. <http://www.chemspider.com>) was used for the estimation of the most probable chemical structure for a given molecular formula.

Antibodies: production, purification, fluorescent labeling, and microarray production

The antibodies used in this study were purified with protein-A and fluorescently labeled with Alexa-647 fluorochrome (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) as described previously (Rivas et al., 2008). The 200 antibodies described by Rivas et al. (2008) were printed onto epoxyactivated microscope slides (Arrayit Corp., Sunnyvale, CA, USA) to form the so-called LDChip200. Printing was performed in such a way that nine identical LDChips were allocated per microscope slide, regularly spaced to match with a cassette containing the same number of hybridization chambers, the multiple-array analysis module (MAAM) device (Parro, 2010).

Sandwich microarray immunoassay (SMI) with LDChip200

Powder and shards from different core samples (0.5 g) were directly analyzed by SMI as described elsewhere (Parro, 2010; Parro et al., 2011). Briefly, the potential molecular biomarkers or cells present in the sample were extracted in 1.5–2.0 mL of buffer TBSTRR (0.4 M Tris-HCl, pH 8, 0.3 M NaCl, 0.1% Tween 20) by means of a handheld ultrasonicator (DR. Hielscher 50W DRH-UP50H sonicator, Hielscher Ultrasonics, Berlin, Germany). The sample was then filtered through a 15- μ m filter, and 40 μ L of the filtrate was incubated in an LDChip200 containing 200 antibodies against microbial cells, environmental extracts biological polymers, such as lipoteichoic acids and peptidoglycan, proteins. (Table S1; Rivas et al., 2008). Up to eight samples plus a control can be simultaneously assayed per microscope slide in a MAAM device. After a washing step to remove the non-specifically bound material and a second incubation with a mixture of 200 fluorescent tracer antibodies, the positive antigen–antibody reactions were read by exciting the fluorochrome at 635 nm and measuring the fluorescence emission at 650 nm in a commercial scanner (GenePix4100A, Genomic Solutions, Huntingdon, UK). The scanned images were analyzed and quantified using commercial microarray analysis software

(GenepixTM Pro Software, Genomic Solutions) as described (Parro et al., 2011; Blanco et al., 2012).

DNA extraction and amplification

Environmental DNA was extracted from 2 g of powdered cores by using the commercially available MoBio DNA extraction kit for soil (MoBio Labs, Solana Beach, CA, USA). The DNA was used as template for simultaneous PCR amplification and fluorescent labeling using the universal primers for the prokaryotic 16S rRNA gene. The primers were 8F (positions 8–27 of *Escherichia coli* 16S rRNA, 5'-AGAGTTTGATCATGGCTCAG), and either 1492R (positions 1492–1474, 5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT) or 16SR (positions 1057–1074, 5'-CACGAGCTGACGACAGCCG). The thermocycler was programmed as follows: 95°C, 5 min; 109 (95 °C 20 s, 50 °C 30 s, 68 °C 60 s); 259 (95 °C 20 s, 48 °C 30 s, 68 °C 60 s + 5 s per cycle); 68°C 10 min; 4°C. Because the quality and yield of the obtained DNA were very low, most of the samples were subjected to whole metagenome amplification by isothermal multiple displacement amplification (MDA) with phi29 DNA polymerase (GenomiPhi DNA Amplification Kit, GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, UK), formerly Amersham Bioscience). The amplified product was used for PCR amplification or directly labeled with a fluorophore and analyzed with the PAM oligonucleotide microarray (see below).

Oligonucleotide microarray hybridization

Garrido et al., 2008 previously reported the so-called prokaryotic acidophile microarray (PAM), an oligonucleotide microarray containing specific 16S and 23S rRNA gene probes for prokaryotic acidophiles (see Garrido et al., 2008; Table S1). Although PAM was specially developed for the detection of prokaryotic acidophiles in the extremely acidic environment of Río Tinto (Huelva, Spain), it also contains specific oligonucleotide probes for the 16S and 23S rRNA genes from other phylogenetic groups, such as a-, b-, c-, and Deltaproteobacteria, low-GC-content Firmicutes, highGC-content Gram-positive bacteria, Archaea, Euryarchaeota, Chrenarchaeota, Methanobacteria, Eukarya. Fluorescently labeled 16S rRNA gene amplicons were checked by agarose gel electrophoresis, then purified with Qiagen PCR purification kit columns (Qiagen, CA, USA), and set to hybridize to the microarray in Hyblt hybridization buffer (Arrayit Corp.) at 50°C for 12 h in a water bath. Then, they were washed and scanned for fluorescence (Garrido et al., 2008). The specificity and the cross-hybridization of the probes in PAM microarray were tested by hybridization with the PCR-amplified 16S rRNA gene of the corresponding type strain (Garrido et al., 2008).

Cloning sequencing and phylogenetic analysis

The extracted DNA either directly or after one round of MDA was used as a template for 16S rRNA gene amplification by PCR. Archaeal sequences were amplified using the archaeal-specific primer 20F (TTCCGGTTGATCCYGC CRG) paired with the universal primer U1392R (ACGGG CCGTGTGTRC), while bacterial sequences were amplified as described in the previous section. Cloning into plasmid vectors, sequencing, and phylogeny studies were performed as previously described (Parro et al., 2011).

Fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Samples of rock particles from the cores were gently washed to remove the fixative and the pore water. Drained rock samples were immersed in 0.5% agarose to avoid detaching bacteria from the sample particles during incubation and washing. Hybridization and staining with DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) were carried out as previously described (Amann, 1995). Cy-3, Cy-5, and fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-labeled probes for fluorescence in situ hybridization FISH were provided by Bonsai Technology (Barcelona, Spain). Catalyzed reporter deposition (CARD) was performed using the method previously described by Pernthaler et al., (2002). Horseradish peroxidase-labeled probes and the fluorochromes AlexaFluor488 and AlexaFluor534 were purchased from Molecular Probes (Invitrogen). Citifluor mounting medium (Citifluor Ltd, London, UK) was added to preparations to avoid fluorescence fading. An Axioskop microscope (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with the proper filter set was used to visualize the FISH results. FISH and CARD-FISH results were further visualized under a fluorescence microscopy (Axioskop II, Zeiss) and LSM510 scanning confocal microscope (Zeiss) equipped with an Ar ion laser (458–514 nm) and two He/Ne lasers (543 and 633 nm). The probes used were EUB338 (GCT GCC TCC CGT AGG AGT), EUB338-II (GCA GCC ACC CGT AGG TGT), and EUB338-III (GCT GCC ACC CGT AGG TGT) (Amann, 1995 and Daims et al., 1999), which are specific for bacteria, and ARCH915 (GTG CTC CCC CGC CAA TTC CT) (Stahl & Amann, 1991), which is specific for the Archaea domain. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of cores samples was performed as previously described (Fernández-Remolar et al., 2008b).

RESULTS

Subsurface geochemistry

Core samples were analyzed by ion chromatography to identify the most relevant anions that could support microbial metabolisms (Fig. 2). Nitrate and nitrite were detected along the core length, the latter being more abundant with peaks of >45 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ at 94.7 and 156 m below the surface (mbs). High amounts of soluble sulfate were also measured, with

maximal values of 18 mg g⁻¹ at 94.7 and 156.4 mbs. Especially relevant was the detection of low-molecular-weight organic acids, such as acetate and formate, with maximum concentrations of >65.15 and > 15 µg g⁻¹, respectively, at 94.7 mbs. In addition, significant amounts of oxalate were also detected in one of the samples (156.4 mbs).

The concentration of soluble ferric iron (Fe³⁺) was 20–50 µM in most of the samples, whereas that of ferrous iron (Fe²⁺) showed a peak around 1.3 mM at 102 mbs. The Fe²⁺ concentration was very low from 156 mbs to the bottom of the borehole, an interval where most of the iron was in its oxidized state. Additionally, H₂ concentration was relatively constant at around 10 ppm in the anaerobic zone, while that of CH₄ increased from 142.5 mbs to the bottom of the borehole to a maximum of 31 ppm (V).

Detection of complex organic matter and biological polymers

Two crude extracts containing biological material (peptides or exopolymeric substances), one from a core containing altered pyrite at 139.38 mbs and the other from the surface of the drilling site, were analyzed using TLC with UV light and vanillin as the revealing agents. Dark spots were obtained with both detection techniques (Fig. 3A, B), revealing the presence of aromatic and steroid-like compounds. The spots from the 139.38 mbs sample were eluted from the TLC membrane and further analyzed by ion electrospray and time-of-flight (QTOF) spectrometry to identify their molecular composition and structure. The comparison of the assigned molecular formulae with those in the databases rendered a probable chemical structure for the main ions produced during the electrospray ionization procedure, which corresponded to aromatic, steroid, or triterpene-like compounds (Fig. 3, numbers 1–6).

Detection of microbial biomarkers using the antibody microarray LDChip200

Pulverized samples were processed by ultrasonication in an aqueous buffer and assayed with the LDChip200, an antibody microarray-based biosensor containing 200 antibodies against multiple biomolecules (Rivas et al., 2008). The results indicated the presence of antigens recognized by the immobilized antibodies onto the microarray. These positive reactions corresponded to antibodies produced against antigens from Gram-positive bacteria (lipoteichoic acids, peptidoglycan), some steroid-like compounds, dsDNA, and biochemical extracts previously obtained from similar core samples (Rivas et al., 2008). In addition, the LDChip200 detected ferritins and DPS-like proteins (Fig. 4) in some of the samples, as well as peptides related to L-asparaginase protein.

Prokaryotic diversity

Total environmental DNA was extracted to determine the microbial diversity by using molecular ecological techniques: (i) an oligonucleotide microarray specially designed for the detection of a broad group of prokaryote phyla (PAM microarray; Table S1; Materials and methods), and (ii) and sequencing of environmental 16S rRNA genes. The hybridization with 16S rRNA amplicons showed strong positive reactions with specific oligonucleotide probes for the Gram-positive low-GC-content Firmicutes phylum (LGC354a, b, c) (Fig. 5) in some of the samples (at 120.85 and 126.85 mbs) that previously exhibited a strong positive reaction with the anti-Grampositive bacterial antibodies (Fig. 4). Among the members of the Firmicutes phylum that could contribute to these signals is the genus *Desulfotomaculum*, which gave a clear positive in the sample at 120.85 mbs (probe DFMI229). Other positive reactions corresponded to high-GC content gram-positive bacteria (HGC236), the Actinobacteria genus *Ferrimicrobium* (probe FRM032), some *Acidithiobacillus spp* (*A. ferrooxidans* and *A. caldus*, probes ACT465a and THC642, respectively), *Thiomonas spp* group 2 (TM2G138), *Desulfovibrio spp* (DSV698), Euryarchaeota (ANME2c760), and Methanococcales (MC1109).

The hybridization of the PAM microarray with the whole MDA-amplified metagenome confirmed the previous results and allowed the hybridization with other probes (Data S1). In particular, it revealed the presence of members of the Betaproteobacteria genus *Gallionella* (probe GALTS0084), the Deltaproteobacteria genus *Desulfosarcina/Desulfococcus* (DSS658), the WJ2- like bacterium, or the recurrent presence of high-GC-content gram-positive bacteria (probe HGC1901 from 23S rRNA gene). Among the Archaea, members of the Chrenarchaeota and Euryarchaeota divisions were found (MBGB380 and ANME2c760, respectively), as well as others belonging to the Methanosarcina family (MSSH8- 59) and the Methanococcales order (MC1109).

Finally, PCR-amplified 16S rRNA gene from the samples which gave positive signals in the antibody microarray and/ or PAM microarray was cloned and sequenced (Table S2). Most of the retrieved sequences corresponded to Betaproteobacteria (*Acidovorax*, *Comamonas*, and *Dechloromonas* genus), Gammaproteobacteria (*Pseudomonadaceae* family), and Acidobacteria divisions, which dominated the upper (90–120 mbs) and the lower (140–164 mbs) part of the anaerobic zone. In the intermediate, low sulfate region of this borehole (120–139 mbs), the sequences corresponded to Firmicutes and Actinobacteria phyla. Additionally, several sequences associated with halophilic Euryarchaea were found, in agreement with the positive hybridization with Euryarchaea-specific probes on PAM microarray.

Metabolically active bacterial clusters

To demonstrate the actual presence of microbial cells in the IPB microniches, several core samples from BH8 were stained with DAPI and hybridized with EUB338, a eubacterial-specific probe to 16S rRNA. DAPI-stained samples revealed the presence of clusters of microbial morphologies bound to micro-holes in the rock in several deep core samples (Fig. 6A). Some of these clusters were also efficiently stained by FISH and CARD-FISH, indicating that the bacterial cells were indeed alive and metabolically active (Fig. 6B). In addition, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis of some core samples showed the presence of carbonaceous networks attached to pyrite minerals that can be originated from microbial exopolymers (not shown). Unfortunately, while microbial clusters were indeed detected by microscopy in this study, their number was too low and their distribution too sparse to allow for a reliable quantification of the biomass in the IPB subsurface.

DISCUSSION

A multitechnique approach to explore the geomicrobiology of a deep pyrite body

Although little is known about the small-scale distribution of micro-organisms in solid samples, some authors have stressed the difficulty of uniformly characterizing microbial communities in deep subsurface rocky samples (Haldeman et al., 1993). Others have shown that in lacustrine sediments, microbial activities, such as sulfate reduction, are carried out in submillimeter microniches (Widerlund and Davidson, 2007). Such heterogeneity complicates the microbiological study of these types of samples. Also, the low concentration of microbes in the deep subsurface forces the sampling of a relatively high amount of material, especially in deep rocky samples (as in this work; Fig. 1), where the microbial distribution is dispersed throughout the mineral matrix (Sahl et al., 2007; Von der Weid et al., 2008). To overcome such a drawback, as well as the inherent bias of each analytical method, we retrieved many small (1–2 g) powder samples at short distances and analyzed them with multiple non-culture-dependent techniques (Materials and methods).

First, a biomarker and life detection experiment was performed by using antibody microarray-based biosensor technology. The advantages of LDChip are: (i) that the assay can be performed in the field, just after sampling, which reduces the chances of sample alteration and/or contamination; (ii) very little sample processing is required, just homogenization by a hand-held sonicator, filtering, and incubation; and (iii) up to hundreds of targets (microbes, proteins, and other biomolecules) can be assayed simultaneously. Its most critical limitations

concern the cross-reaction events in a multiplex assay with a multianalyte-containing sample. We have addressed this issue by developing antibody graphs and a deconvolution method to distinguish the specific recognition events between antibodies and their cognate antigens from the cross-reaction with other related antigens (Rivas et al., 2011). We concluded that although cross-reactions take place, they correspond to similar antigens or they come from phylogenetically related microbes. Another critical aspect of multiplex sandwich-type multiplex immunoassay is the inherent background due to the high concentration of the revealing antibody mixture, in this case 200 antibodies. However, we demonstrated that the system still keeps a reliable dynamic range (Rivas et al., 2008). In the present work, LDChip200 mainly detected biological polymers from the Gram-positive bacteria, mostly lipoteichoic acids and peptidoglycan. One of the positive reactions corresponded to an antiferritin antibody, indicating the presence of bacterioferritins or the highly related DPS proteins. These proteins form part of the universal 'Ferritin-like superfamily' that plays a critical role as cellular repository of the excess of iron (Andrews, 2010). They might be induced in the IPB subsurface as a consequence of the high iron concentration that micro-organisms have to deal with. Indeed, ferritins might be playing a detoxifying role by oxidizing Fe^{2+} (highly toxic) to Fe^{3+} and storing it inside the pockets these proteins can form (Andrews, 1998; Smith, 2004). Antibodies to crude environmental extracts from cores at different depths (ID7-12S2) also showed positive reactions with a sandwich-type immunoassay, indicating the presence of complex immunogenic polymers. Whether these polymers came from Gram-positive bacteria has yet to be determined. However, the oligonucleotide microarray clearly revealed the presence of DNA from the Gram-positive Firmicutes phylum and from the genus *Desulfotomaculum*, a group of obligate anaerobe sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB). Interestingly, the LDChip200 detected *Acidithiobacillus caldus* or a related strain in a sample retrieved from 156.4 mbs (not shown), and its presence was corroborated by the positive DNA hybridization with the specific oligonucleotide probe THC642 (Fig. 7). We confirmed once again the usefulness of the LDChip immunosensor for the detection of biomarkers in the subsurface, and its tremendous potential for the search for life on Mars as the key component of Signs Of Life Detector (SOLID) instrument (Parro et al., 2011). The SOLID is an instrument designed and constructed for the in situ search for molecular biomarkers on Mars (Parro et al., 2005; 2008; Parro et al., 2011). The instrument can extract the organic matter present in up to 0.5 g of dust, martian regolith, or ground rock into a liquid solution or suspension by means of ultrasonication. After a filtering process, the liquid filtrate floods a flow chamber containing the multiplex immunosensor LDChip. After incubation and washing steps, a mixture of fluorescently labeled antibodies, a laser beam to excite the fluorochrome, and a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera is used to

reveal the positive antigen–antibody reactions. The results shown here indicate that the SOLID’s life detection system works well with rocky deep subsurface samples from a martian analogue.

The LDChip200 showed a widespread signal from Gram-positive antigens, in agreement with the positive hybridization obtained with oligonucleotide probes for low- and high-GC-content Gram-positive bacteria with the PAM microarray. The PAM contained more probes than LDChip200, whose probe composition was highly biased for detecting micro-organisms from surface environments and lacked antibodies from many groups of prokaryotes. Although the use of multiple displacement amplification (MDA) for the PAM microarray hybridization resulted in lower fluorescent signal and higher background, it corroborated the results obtained with 16S rRNA gene PCRs with DNA extracts not subjected to MDA. Furthermore, it revealed the presence of additional microbial groups. This was the case of the probe to *Gallionella*, a genus from the Betaproteobacteria division that includes iron-oxidizing chemolithotrophs operating at low oxygen concentrations. It also revealed the presence of some members of methanogenic Archaea from the Euryarchaeota phylum, particularly from the *Methanosarcina* family (MSSH859) and Methanococcales order (MC1109), and members of the Deltaproteobacteria *Desulfosarcina/Desulfococcus* genera.

Some of the obtained 16S rRNA gene sequences were in agreement with the results from the immunological and hybridization techniques. This technique also revealed the presence of denitrifying Betaproteobacteria, which were not detected with the previous techniques. The reason for such a bias in the detection of Betaproteobacteria by 16S rRNA gene sequencing compared with the other two techniques may reside in the absence of antibodies in LDChip200 and DNA probes in the oligonucleotide microarray for this phylum (only a generic probe whose target is in 23S rRNA, BET42a) and/or to the natural bias produced in the PCR amplification in natural samples with very little DNA amounts. Furthermore, MDA is known to produce biases in community composition (Yilmaz et al., 2010).

The detection by SEM and FISH of clusters of microbial cells bound to minerals supported the results obtained with the techniques shown above. Although it is impossible to completely exclude the possibility of contamination of the samples with drilling fluids, the absence of the bromide tracer in the analyzed samples, as well as microscopy showing the presence of mineral-bound microbial clusters, indicated that the molecular results indeed corresponded to indigenous micro-organisms of the IPB.

The fact that the results obtained with the different techniques did not match exactly in every single 0.5–1 g of core sample can be a consequence of the heterogeneity of rocky samples, as well as the intrinsic biases of each of the current molecular ecology techniques used (Polz & Cavanaugh, 1998; Yilmaz et al., 2010). In spite of this limitation, the geochemical and biodiversity analyses allowed us to cluster the samples in differentiated geomicrobiological units (Fig. 8; see discussion below).

In conclusion, the microbiological analysis of low-biomass-containing environmental samples, such as those from deep drilling projects, requires the application of several complementary molecular techniques to obtain a more precise picture of the microbial population and the operating metabolisms. The multitechnique approach we have shown here, combining *in situ* immunosensing, multiple displacement metagenome amplification, PCR, oligonucleotide microarray hybridization, and sequencing, is particularly useful to complement the biases that PCR can produce in metagenomic studies, where, very often, the amount and the quality of the template is far from the ideal.

Potential microbial metabolisms in the deep IPB subsurface

Deep subsurface ecosystems are thought to be energy limited, with low cell numbers subsisting at very low metabolic rates (Hoehler & Jørgensen, 2013). In subseafloor sediments, the readily degradable organic substrates disappear quickly with depth, leaving only recalcitrant compounds to support heterotrophic growth (Parkes et al., 2000). Altogether, the geochemical and the immunological results indicated the presence of high molecular-weight and complex organic matter that can originate from extant microbial cells (protein, polysaccharides) or from extinct biomass (aromatic compounds). Small organic acids such as acetate or formate could be used as efficient carbon and energy sources, while rock-water interactions in deep bedrock fracture environments could provide the hydrogen necessary to support lithoautotrophic metabolisms (Stevens & McKinley, 1995; Freund et al., 2002).

Water availability is also a key factor in subsurface environments, as it will strongly affect microbial metabolic rates and diffusion of molecular species. While most of the core samples retrieved in this work were generally compact and non-porous, the presence of cracks in some of the deepest cores (below 150 m; Fig. 2) would result in an increase in the water influx, as well as in the space available for microbial colonization. Interestingly, a diverse prokaryotic community was detected in that zone (Fig. 8C), along with alterations in the

geochemical profiles, such as an increase in sulfate and methane concentrations, and a decrease in ferrous iron (Fig. 2), which could be products of an increased microbial activity. The presence of iron oxides and iron-oxidizing micro-organisms (*Leptospirillum spp.* and *Acidithiobacillus spp.*, Fig. 7) in this zone also suggests that the water entering the system carries dissolved oxygen. Such oxygen would be readily consumed by these pyrite-oxidizing microbes, rendering an anoxic fluid charged with sulfate and ferric iron. This would provide an input of oxidants to the anaerobic part of the community, which contains sulfate- and iron-reducing micro-organisms. In addition, methanogens were also detected (Fig. 7, probes MER1, MG1200, MC1109, MSSH859), together with an increase in methane concentration (Fig. 2). The co-occurrence of high sulfate and methane levels in this zone is interesting, as sulfate is known to inhibit methanogenesis (Winfrey & Zeikus, 1977; Abram & Nedwell, 1978) via substrate competition from SRB. In spite of that, there was no detection of SRB below 150 mbs, while methanogens were found in almost every sample. The reason for the predominance of methanogenesis over sulfate reduction is unclear, but it has been described that SRB can be inhibited by high heavy metal concentrations and precipitation of metal sulfides (Utgikar et al., 2002).

Ferric iron is another inhibitor of methanogenesis (Lovley & Phillips, 1987; Bodegom et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2009). Nevertheless, Sanz et al. (2011) reported methanogenic activity in microcosms from ferric iron-rich sediments of the Tinto River, as well as in situ measurements. They concluded that methanogenesis was being carried out in reduced microniches generated by iron-respiring bacteria. Our results support this hypothesis in the sense that the distribution of methanogens and ferric iron reducers (e.g. *Ferrimicrobium spp.*) followed a similar pattern throughout the whole borehole (Fig. 7, probes FRM0732, MER1, MC1109).

The fact that methane was only detected below 140 mbs in spite of methanogens being ubiquitous in the borehole can be explained by the presence of methane oxidizers in all but the deepest samples (Fig. 7b, d). Above 149 mbs, there seems to be a close association between anaerobic methane oxidizers (ANMEs) and SRB (Fig. 7c, d), which could mean that methane oxidation coupled to sulfate reduction (Orphan et al., 2001; Parkes et al., 2007; Knittel & Boetius, 2009; Pedersen, 2013) would be the main methane sink in the borehole (Fig. 8B).

The presence of 16S rRNA sequences from denitrifying bacteria (Fig. 7, Betaproteobacteria) is more difficult to link to the geochemical data, as the nitrate and nitrite

distributions do not seem to follow a clear pattern. Nitrite peaks observed at several depths could be interpreted as the product of nitrate reduction, although their distribution is not entirely consistent with the detection of denitrifiers in the borehole.

Because the water table was located at 90 m below the surface, we assume a smooth transition from an aerobic/ microaerobic level to an anaerobic one (below 115 m deep). Detection of aerobic and microaerophilic pyrite oxidizers such as *Galionella* spp. and *Thiomonas* spp. above 115 mbs (Fig. 7a) does in fact suggest that some aerobic microniches exist in that zone (Fig. 8A). In this part of the drill, microorganisms such as *Galionella* spp might be oxidizing metals (Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+}), and others such as *Thiomonas* spp and *Acidithiobacillus* spp could oxidize Fe^{2+} and reduced sulfur compounds (e.g. thiosulfate, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$). Moreover, in those microaerobic niches, the methanotrophic bacteria *Methylomonas* spp. (Fig. 7b) could account for the aerobic oxidation of methane while anaerobic methanotrophs (Fig. 7d) would do the same in the anaerobic niches

The integration of geochemical, immunological, DNA hybridization, and sequencing results, allowed us to propose a three-compartment model for the deep IPB subsurface ecosystem (Fig. 8); (i) a microaerophilic zone (84– 116 mbs), in which methane, iron, and sulfur (including pyrite, FeS_2) are oxidized in aerobic microniches, while denitrification and methanogenesis associated with ferric iron reduction occurs in the anaerobic ones; (ii) an anaerobic zone (115–149 mbs), in which anaerobic methane oxidation might be coupled to sulfate reduction; and (iii) a fractured zone (150–164 mbs), in which an increased water and oxygen availability would allow for higher metabolic rates. Pyrite oxidation would consume dissolved oxygen, generating anaerobic microniches in which methanogenesis would be the main process. Thus, microbial activities would be responsible for the disappearance of reduced iron and the generation of sulfate and methane at those depths (Fig. 2).

In conclusion, we showed evidence for a rich prokaryotic diversity operating in the deep subsurface of the massive sulfide ores of the IPB. The LDChip200 immunosensor identified microbial polymers from Gram-positive bacteria as well as some proteins from the ferritin family at different depths. This result was confirmed with the PAM oligonucleotide microarray, which detected Gram-positive bacteria from the Firmicutes and Actinobacteria phyla. Additionally, PAM detected sulfate-reducing bacteria, methanogenic Archaea, anaerobic methane oxidizers, as well as bacteria involved in the iron/sulfur cycle. These results allowed us to infer a model of the deep subsurface habitat of the IPB (Fig. 8). However, many questions

are still unanswered: the origin of acetate and formate remains to be clarified, the presence of acetogenic and hydrogenotrophic bacteria must be confirmed, and other metabolic traits not yet identified should be searched for. A deeper molecular and phylogenetic analysis of the microbial diversity along the borehole will contribute to clarify some of these questions. The European Research Council has granted the IPB Subsurface Life (IPBSL) project, an Advanced Grant project, now underway to perform deeper drillings and address these and other questions concerning the geomicrobiology of this unique massive pyrite site.

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Figures

Fig. 1 Exploration of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) subsurface geomicrobiology. Geographical location of the IPB in the Iberian Peninsula (A) and a satellite view (B) of Pena de Hierro (Nerva, Spain), where the 2004 MARTE project drilling campaign was carried out (star). Another drilling site currently under study is highlighted (circle). Note the gray/light blue material at the side

walls of the lake, which corresponds to the massive pyrite stock work. The vertical distance between the drilling site and the lake water table was about 90 m. (C) Profile of one of the cores recovered from 130 mbs. (D) Cross section of the same core. Numbered squares (amplified on the right) indicate interesting features in the core, such as oxidized red spots (arrowheads) or the high abundance of bright pyrite crystals (small arrows).

Fig. 2. Simplified lithostratigraphical section of borehole 8 showing lithology, water usage, acetate, formate, oxalate, nitrate, and bromine concentration in rock leachates. Hydrogen, methane, iron (II), and iron (III) concentrations were measured in solutions. Sodium bromide was used as a chemical tracer included in the drilling fluid, and the bromide concentration from the rock leachate was used to calculate the contamination factor. Water usage indicates the percentage of the drilling fluid loss through fractures during boring. All the concentration values are expressed in parts per million (ppm).

Fig. 3. Thin-layer chromatography of extracts from samples at the surface (a) and 139.38 m (b) depth. The result was revealed with short-wave UV light (A), indicating the presence of aromatic rings and conjugation, and with vanillin staining (B). Also shown are the most probable molecular structures obtained after the analysis of the 139.38 m spots (arrows) by ion electrospray (ESI+ and ESI-) and time-of-flight QTOF spectrometry: 1-3, ion 437.1938, which may correspond, respectively, to the molecular formula C₂₂H₃₃N₂O₃S₂, C₂₂H₃₃N₂O₃, or C₂₂H₂₅N₆O₄; 4 and 6, ion 637.3050, which may correspond, respectively, to the molecular formula C₄₀H₃₉N₅O₃ and C₃₄H₅₃O₅; 5, ion 343.9950, which may correspond to the molecular formula C₁₀H₁₀N₅O₃. More details can be found in Supporting Table S3.

Fig. 4. Biomarker detection in deep IPB subsurface by the life detector chip LDChip200. A core sample (0.5 g) extracted at 150.15 mbs was analyzed with LDChip 200 by sandwich microarray immunoassay as indicated in Materials and methods. (A) The LDChip output is a 16-bits image with bright fluorescent spots (red to white, top picture) that showed positive antigen–antibody reactions. The fluorescent intensity can be quantified and plotted to form an immunogram (B). Due to the specificity of the antigen–antibody reaction, each positive signal in the chip immediately identifies the target compound: 1, steroid-like similar to estradiol; 2, ds/ssDNA; 3, Cyanidium spp rich natural extract; 4, Gram-positive antigen; 5, viral antigen; 6, dsDNA; 7, ferritin protein; 8, Hydrogenobacter spp-rich natural extract; 9, 10, 11, 12, antigens derived from extracts of IPB subsurface cores at 118–126 m, 138–139 m, 147–141 m, and 84–97 m deep, respectively (antibody names ID10S2, ID11S2, ID12S2, and ID7S2); 13, L-asparaginase protein; 14, GroEL protein; 15, bacterial Lipid A; 16, lipoteichoic acid (LTA) and Listeria

monocytogenes LTA; 17, Lipid A, KDO bacterial antigen, and McrB protein; 18, NirS, NOR, and NRA; 19, penicillin derivatives; 20, peptidoglycan; 21, a pre-immune antiserum; 22, *Salmonella* spp; 23, cAMP; and 24, tryptophan.

Fig. 5. Exploring the prokaryotic diversity of the IPB with an oligonucleotide microarray. Environmental DNA was extracted from different core samples, the 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR, fluorescently labeled and hybridized with PAM microarray (Materials and methods). Scanned fluorescent images obtained after hybridization of the amplified DNA from core samples 120.85 (A) and 126.85 mbs (B). Probes showing positive results (red to white spots) are indicated: EUB338 and Y2R, universal for Eubacteria; DFMI229, genus *Desulfotomaculum* (Firmicutes, Clostridiales); DSV698, sulfate reducer Deltaproteobacteria, Desulfovibrionaceae, most *Desulfovibrio* species and *Desulfomonas*; LGC354a, b, c, Low-GC Gram-positive Firmicutes *Lactobacillus* group (a), *Bacillus* group (b), and *Streptococcus* group (c); Arch915, Archaea; ANME2c760, Methanotrophic, Euryarchaeota; DELTA495a, Deltaproteobacteria and Gemmatimonadetes; HGC236, High-GC content Gram-positive Actinobacteria (Supporting Table S1 and Supporting Data S1).

Fig. 6. Optical microscopy analysis of cores from the Iberian Pyrite Belt subsurface. (A), (B) Epifluorescence micrographs showing a eubacterial cell cluster at 154.7 mbs stained with DAPI (A), and the same field stained by FISH with the Eubacteria-specific probe EUB338 (B), and by CARD-FISH (insert in B) with the same probe.

Fig. 7. Comparison between the results obtained with three different molecular techniques: Map of relative fluorescent intensities obtained after hybridization of the PCR-amplified 16S rRNA gene and total MDA-amplified metagenome with PAM oligonucleotide microarray; the fluorescent intensity of the most relevant positive biomarkers detected with the immunosensor LDChip200; and a positive (red) or negative detection (black) map of the retrieved 16S rRNA gene sequences. Each horizontal row of red and black squares represents

the result for each probe obtained for a sample in the same chip. The geological profile and the depths at which the core samples were collected for analysis are indicated (left). The specificities of the PAM probes are detailed in the supplementary materials (Table S1). The LDChip200 probes listed in this figure are the following: GP Ag, Gram-positive bacteria antigens (mostly lipoteichoic acids); ID7S2, immunoreactive EPS material from some of the cores. Based on the prokaryotic diversity results, three geomicrobiological levels can be distinguished (white horizontal lines), which are further discussed in the text. Letters from 'a' to 'h' indicate clusters of probes with differentiated patterns whose distribution is further discussed in the text.

Fig. 8. Potential metabolisms operating in the IPB subsurface. Based on the geochemical, immunological, DNA hybridization, and sequencing results, we propose a three-compartment model for the deep IPB subsurface ecosystem: (A) Microaerophilic zone (84–116 mbs); (B) Anaerobic zone (115–149 mbs); and (C) Fractured zone (150–164 mbs). See Discussion for details.